
Deliverable JIP1-4.1

Two internal training workshops for ORION partners

Workpackage 4

Responsible Partner: 38-SVA

Contributing partners: 9-BfR

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	JIP1-4.1 Two internal training workshops for ORION partners
WP and Task	WP4, Task T-4.4
Leader	SVA
Other contributors	BfR
Due month of the deliverable	M12
Actual submission month	M12
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.</i> <i>OTHER</i>	R
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU

ORION TRAINING AND DISSEMINATION

Executive Summary

In Task 4.4 of the ORION project trainings were planned and conducted that aimed at sharing the knowledge already available within the consortium among all project partners. This also included training of partners in the use of new tools produced/adopted. Later in the project Task 4.4 will also contribute to the dissemination of new ORION results by providing trainings for external partners.

According to the ORION project plan, the deliverable D4.1 specifies that until M12 the ORION project has to provide “Two internal training workshops for ORION partners”.

The ORION project performed the following training activities in 2018; some of them also open for EFSA / ECDC and selected other EJP projects:

- 28th May 2018 Webinar WP4 VRE Features <https://goo.gl/VQJdpL>
- 25th June 2018 Webinar WP1 <https://goo.gl/cuHtnq>
- 30th August 2018 Webinar WP2 Epi
- 25th September 2018 WP3 webinar series [Video](#)
- 6th November 2018 Webinar: first version of ORION glossary